

*Extending Anthophila research through
image and trait digitization (Big-Bee)
annual cumulative report*

Prepared by: Katja C. Seltsmann

Edited and reviewed by: Sylvia Reyes, Mark Smith, Jorrit Poelen, Lindsay Walker, Erika Tucker, Crystal Maier, István Mikó

Year 2: September 01, 2022 - August 31, 2023

Accomplishments:

Major Project Goals:

The goal of Big-Bee is to expand bee research through the digitization of bee traits and images. To accomplish this goal, we will create over 1.2M images of over 5K bee species and share these images via the Bee Library and through published curated datasets. These goals will be accomplished using many methods, including developing novel Notes from Nature measurement tools.

The digitization goals of Big-Bee are (Table 1):

1. 572,813 newly digitized specimens of 5,509 target taxa. The focus is on complete digitization, which includes georeferencing and images with both specimens and labels.
2. ca. 109,000 high-resolution, multifocal stacked Exemplar and Diagnostic images, including focal taxa and bee parasites.
3. 10,300 3D Image Suites for 3D image reconstruction.
4. Score Morphological Traits from images, including Body Size, Hair Color, and Hairiness.
5. Score Life History Traits from literature, including Phenology, Nesting Biology, Sociality, and Biotic Associations (Floral Specialization, Parasites, and Pathogens).

Data and images will be discoverable via iDigBio, GBIF, Bee Library (Symbiota database), and as published curated datasets.

Digitizing institution	Digitized specimens	Focus-stacked images	3D image suites	Additional Images
Arizona State University (ASUHC)	10,000	0	0	
California Academy of Sciences (CAS)	142,325	5,474	500	
Florida State Collection of Arthropods (FSCA)	90,495	5,294	500	
Harvard University (MCZ)	52,324	6,492	500	
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	2000	0	0	2,000 (microCT)
Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County (LACM)	72,681	6,543	500	
San Diego Natural History Museum (SDMC)	14,224	797	3,000	

Digitizing institution	Digitized specimens	Focus-stacked images	3D image suites	Additional Images
University of California-Berkeley (EMEC)	69,297	9,892	100	
University of California, Santa Barbara (UCSB)	8,697	5,092	4,000	
University of Colorado (UCMC)	62,677	10,160	100	
University of Kansas (SEMC)	9,495	28,185	100	
University of Michigan Museum of Zoology (UMMZ)	27,815	15,198	500	
University of New Hampshire Collection of Insects and Arthropods (UNHC)	6,783	12850	500	1,000 (CLSM)
USGS Native Bee Inventory and Monitoring Lab (USGS BIML)	4000	4,000	0	
Total:	572,813	109,977	10,300	3,000

Table 1: Digitization goals outlining the 572K specimens to be published and digitized using multiple imaging modalities; 109K high-resolution, focal stacked exemplar and diagnostic images; 10,300 3D image suites consisting of ~64 focal stacked images per suite; and 3,000 CT or CLSM images. Grey highlighted rows are non-funded partners.

Biodiversity Informatics goals are:

1. Create the Bee Library as a Symbiota portal dedicated to bees and bee traits;
 - a. expand Symbiota’s ability to link to external resources, including the ability to link to: externally managed literature (via Weblink DOI), observations (e.g., iNaturalist), other image datasets (e.g., CT, CLSM, and 3D models held outside of ASU), and other related specimens;
 - b. investigate options for sharing Image View (e.g., dorsal, ventral) as a property in Audubon Core in Symbiota;
 - c. extend the Symbiota Trait Management Tools developed by the CAP TCN to manage bee traits from both literature and specimen sources;
 - d. extend the image and dataset search capabilities in Symbiota based on locality, taxon, and view; and
 - e. Add bee observation collections.

2. publish versioned datasets of the textual trait data and “training datasets” of image data as products;
3. establish connections between Bee-Bee Global Biotic Interactions, iDigBio, and GBIF;
4. investigate computer vision for traits and improved methods for 3D image reconstruction;
5. integrate additional bee data from network collections, monitoring programs, and federal collections (e.g., USGS, USDA, Smithsonian) via established IPTs or spreadsheet uploads; and
6. participate in the OpenTraits Network.

Outreach, workforce training, and broader impact goals:

1. Create a Research Advisory Board;
2. provide digitization resources for all global bee collections, including the ability to digitize specimens through the Big-Bee Symbiota portal and support from a portal data manager to help train and facilitate the upload and data sharing;
3. participate fully with the Bee Monitoring USDA-RCN;
4. create a science-themed radio program about bees;
5. contribute lesson plans to BLUE (Biodiversity Literacy for Undergraduate Education);
6. continue efforts to recruit students from underrepresented groups;
7. provide opportunities for all participants to advance skills in biodiversity information science, bee identification, high-resolution imaging, museum curation, and outreach.
 - a. 3D and high-resolution imaging provided by Mark Smith, owner and developer of Macroscopic Solutions, LLC;
 - b. data curation and workflows using the Symbiota portal, including georeferencing, data management, trait annotation, and Bee Library dataset creation;
 - c. annotating and defining traits in the Bee Library;
 - d. creating a citizen science bee inventory using the Bee Library to create identification tools.
 - e. online bee morphology and Bee Library workshops will be developed in years two and three of the project. The first will focus on bee male genitalia and it will include how to prepare specimens and use the Bee Library for identification by comparing images to dissected specimens. In year three, a two-day virtual workshop on bee identification and trait determination will train novel bee researchers on how best to use the Bee Library to inform their identification efforts.
 - f. two undergraduate computer science projects will be developed by a Postdoctoral Researcher at UCSB for incorporation into the recently funded NSF “HDR DSC: Collaborative Research: Central Coast Data Science Partnership: Training a New Generation of Data Scientists” initiative.

Accomplishments Under These Goals:

Continuing Project: All 13 institutions funded by the grant continue to be engaged and successfully contributing to the project (UNHC, UMMZI, UCSB, FSCA, LACM, UNR, SEMC, SDMC, UCMC, CAS, EMEC, ASUHIC, MCZ - see participant list at end of document for institution details). New contributing partners include New Brunswick Museum and the USDA ARS in Logan, Utah. Neither of the new partners is funded by the Big-Bee grant.

Digitization Workflows: All partner institutions continue digitizing specimens with images of labels. ASUHIC & UCSB have already exceeded their original goals for Specimen with Label digitization. Year 2 primarily focused on 3D digitization with an ongoing **3D Modeling Short Course** led by Mark Smith, Macroscopic Solutions. Macroscopic Solutions actively manages

two channels found publicly on the Big-Bee's support network hosted by Slack (https://join.slack.com/t/big-beeworkspace/shared_invite/zt-1yfgtbfa9-bbFQsqMf9Od9FWPrO3FWag). In response to support requests via Slack and during regular office hours (Wed 4 PM EST), a series of presentations and instructional videos have been produced. A total of 16 help and tutorial videos were created and shared on the Macroscopic Solutions YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@macropod/videos>).

Macroscopic Solutions has seen increasing interest in 3D photogrammetry since Big-Bee began in 2020. Some end users have opted to join Big-Bee's working group on Slack to participate in 3D photogrammetry collaboration. Some of these institutions include the University of Washington's Geology Dept., the USDA, the **Space Force**, and the **US Air Force Academy**, which have similar research objectives for samples related and unrelated to entomology.

UMMZ, SEMC, UNH, FSCA, and UCMC all modified their institutional database in some way this year to facilitate the sharing of images and data. These modifications varied in level of difficulty. During the first year of the project, FSCA data was entered into The Museum of Biological Diversity database (mbd-db.osu.edu), with an informal agreement that an IPT would be provided to direct specimen records and images directly to the Big Bee Library. This IPT was not developed, and problems with the database have made it impossible to export records entered during the final months of 2022 and the first part of 2023, at which point they stopped using that database and switched to Ecdysis (Symbiota-ASU). FSCA exported records from the beginning of the project until November 2022. All images had to be separately uploaded as there is no batch export function. These events caused an unfortunate loss of time and productivity, but the move has now supported FSCA publication of data on GBIF and increased the security of the data.

Figure 1: Example 3D image workflow created by the 2023 Data Science Capstone group at UCSB. See full-size poster at <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0hd7v9jt>

Digitization: 220,779 images have been captured for Big-Bee (September 15, 2021 - July 01, 2023). This is up from **64,454 reported last year**.

Label with Specimen Image Digitization: Big-Bee will image, transcribe, and georeference **572,813** new specimens as part of the project. We have already completed approximately **48%** of our imaging goals (Figure 2; Table 2).

Figure 2: Label with Specimen digitization progress. Label with Specimen images are newly digitized specimens that need imaging, transcription of data to databases, and georeferencing.

	Complete	Remaining
Specimen Images	186,696	386,117
Transcribed	53,699	519,114
Georeferenced	39,272	533,541

Exemplar, Diagnostic, and 3D Image Digitization: 22,618 Exemplar Images, 712 Diagnostic Images, and 59 3D models were created so far for the project. 10,713 multifocal stacked images were generated in the creation of 59 models. These are multi-stacked images photographed with the Macropod Pro imaging system (Table 3).

	Complete	Remaining
Exemplar & Diagnostic Images	23,330	86,647
3D imaged specimens	99	10,201
3D image stacks	10,713	652,864
CLSM/CT	40	2,960

Table 3: High-resolution imaging progress

Specialized Diagnostic Imaging: UNHC collected **over 40 CLSM 3D datasets** (dorsal and ventral view) and 240 brightfield images of male genitalia thus far in the project. Specimens are from DNA sequencing work of Sophie Cardinal (CNCI) and Florida Department of Agriculture (FDACS). Specimens from FDACS have been identified by experts, and specimens from CNCI have been DNA barcoded. These specimens were sent to the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology for synchrotron-based micro CT (Thomas van de Kamp). However, this project phase is delayed

due to resource limitations (one beamtime week instead of 3 beamtime weeks for the biological imaging station) caused by a power shortage of the Synchrotron facility as a consequence of the war in Ukraine. UCSB has submitted a separate USDA proposal to acquire a microCT at UCSB that could be used in the last year of Big-Bee (if funded). Several microCT images of target taxa were imaged as test datasets. These will be shared along with other Big-Bee images. Sharing these large and high-resolution images will be done via micropublications linked to records in the Bee Library in year 3.

Figure 2: Specialized diagnostic imaging includes microCT (left-UCSB) and CLSM (right-UNHC).

Digitization Progress Per Institution:

All Big-Bee digitizing institutions have begun digitization with significant progress starting in the last quarter of the first year. The details for each institution's progress are listed in Table 4.

	UNHC	UMMZI	UCSB	FSCA	SEMC	SDMC	UCMC	CAS	EMEC	LACM	ASUHC	MCZ
Label with Specimen Images	700	8517	5154	13619	0	2857	54223	21923	34695	18493	1892	24623
New specimens data transcribed	0	2775	4059	16110	0	180	1442	2537	5640	687	0	20269
New specimens georeferenced	0	0	3113	16110	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	20049
Focus-stacked Exemplar Images	1062	3641	1325	775	6600	432	1325	1010	2553	0	1892	2003
Focus-stacked Diagnostic Images	391	0	321	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Number of 3D models	40	0	31	0	0	24	3	0	0	0	0	1

Table 4: Digitization progress per Institution

Macroscopic Solutions:

Macroscopic Solutions assembled, delivered, and continues to support the Macropod PRO 3D imaging systems Big-Bee uses for the high-resolution focal stacked imaging and 3D photogrammetry. In 2020, when the systems were procured and distributed for Big-Bee, several new light diffusers and adapters were included to improve sample alignment and lighting adjustability. A new tripod base is currently in design that will incorporate and reduce the number of adapters the Macropod requires, thus, decreasing weight and improving ergonomics. A new wireless and rechargeable flash system has been sourced and outfitted for future systems, the Godox MF12 with a wireless remote trigger. The flash allows for a 35% increase in capture rate, and 2 of the 4 included flash units can be recharged while the other 2 are in use. The cable reduction also allows for better placement, enhancing light diffusion, which is critical for the final construction of any model.

Macroscopic Solutions has proactively reported setbacks and flaws used for 3D photogrammetric reconstruction to Agisoft Metashape. As a result, several model tweaks had been incorporated into the workflow to create better-looking models. Agisoft released Metashape 2.0 in February 2023 and many of these tweaks were incorporated into the default workflow, thus improving the tool for insect 3D reconstruction. Macroscopic Solutions has observed a ~60% decrease in the overall time required for model completion by eliminating the requirement for a dense cloud reconstruction before mesh triangulation. The overall data points required for initial alignment have also been reduced to one single 360-degree orbit every 4 degrees resulting in 90 original data points of focus stacked images. We expect the overall time requirement to further reduce and build quality to improve as future updates are released.

Figure 3: We have included a new expedition for finding pollen on bees called Pollen Finder

Notes from Nature: To facilitate label transcription and to measure body size, UNR built a custom Notes from Nature project for Big-Bee called the Big-Bee Bonanza. The project includes a designated bee-themed landing page and several pages outlining how community scientists can get involved in the Big-Bee project. It also includes information about the research goals, project team members, a place to track project statistics, and a forum for online discussion. The Big-Bee Notes from Nature Project includes 4 custom workflows to suit the needs of researchers and ensure standardized data outputs. Two of these workflows are focused on the transcription of label information. The third is for measuring bee tegula, a proxy for body size. The fourth, called Pollen Finder (Figure 3), asked participants to identify bees that are carrying pollen. LACM, UCSB, EMEC, & CAS have used the project resulting in 37,126 completed

subjects (51,472 total subjects) and **1,756** volunteers. This is up from 2,000 completed subjects and 377 volunteers at the last annual report.

<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>

Bee Library Symbiota Portal: The Big-Bee Symbiota portal (Bee Library - <https://library.big-bee.net>) was rapidly launched in the first quarter of the project (October 2021). The portal is managed by the Symbiota Support Hub at ASU.

The bee library hosts **2,123,637** occurrence records from **17** specimen collections and **1** observation collection containing iNaturalist observations. **86%** of the specimens are georeferenced, **40%** contain images (841,396 images), and **87%** are identified to species (retrieved July 21, 2023). All Big-Bee participants are sharing data with the Bee Library.

During this year, Symbiota Support Hub activities included:

- Documented how Big-Bee adds images to the Bee Library and presented this information alongside other Symbiota workflows at the Biodiversity Digitization Conference: <https://symbiota.org/digitization-workflows/>
- Performed periodic code updates of the Big-Bee GitHub code repository (<https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/Symbiota-light>) by pulling developments from the BioKIC/Symbiota project. These updates include adding new features, bug fixes, and security patches. Code updates to the production data portal code are coordinated with the GitHub updates. SSH IT administrator Greg Post has been added as an admin to the GitHub project to assist with these tasks.
- Provided TCN PI Katja Seltmann access to the backend database via PhpMyAdmin web application to improve reporting for the TCN.
- Made improvements to the image tagging scripts. Scripts are run each night as a Cron Job to ensure all new images are tagged within 24 hours of loading.
- Batch added ~30,000 newly digitized specimen records and ~10,000 images to the portal for other institutions on this TCN.
- User support, including migrating FSCA by migrating all data and images to Ecdysis.
- The Symbiota Support Hub (<https://symbiota.org>) and Big-Bee have organized a bee data publication campaign that includes a lot of individual attention and support for people hoping to publish datasets to GBIF and the Bee Library. All datasets, including bee collections found at institutions or owned by individuals, observation datasets, monitoring datasets, museum collections, and datasets associated with publications, will be considered. Datasets will be publishable to GBIF from the portal, and data providers will be provided training and access to manage the datasets on the portal. Registration is currently open for the campaign at: <https://symbiota.org/upcoming-bee-campaign/>

Image Sharing: Working with ASU Hub Ed Gilbert & Andrew Johnston in year 1, Big-Bee defined the first set of image descriptive terms to use in searching the Bee Library for images. To do this, we adopted an abbreviated list based on the MZC list of standard imaging views. The views are incorporated in Symbiota Bee Library as a “Tag” that can be applied to images, resulting in a person's ability to retrieve all images of a specific bee view. The example pictured below (Figure 3) is the view of an image search with the lateral habitus filter applied to view images of the whole body from the lateral perspective. In year 2, Gilbert expanded the linking tool to **batch link images** (Figure 4). This functionality is a critical step toward tagging the thousands of images created before Big-Bee. The batch tagging feature is currently being tested by DigIn and Big-Bee TCNs. This workflow was featured in a Symbiota-specific

symposium at the Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections' annual meeting (Smith & Seltmann, 2023).

Figure 4: Symbiota's new batch tool for tagging images with specimen view and part information.

Global Biotic Interactions: 242,692 biotic interactions are shared from Big-Bee institutions to Global Biotic Interactions (GloBI) as of July 24, 2022. This is up from 134,802 last year at this time. **130,907 are bee interactions. Data from the project are versioned in quarterly reports archived on Zenodo:**

Seltmann, Katja C., & Poelen, Jorrit H. (2022). Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.8.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722444>

And bee interactions are published as a dataset:

Katja C. Seltmann, & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2022). Global Bee Interaction Data (v2.02) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564718>

Seltmann and Poelen continue to support a data monitoring page at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee> to help review and keep track of the availability of Big-Bee associated natural history collections. The reviews link via shared IPT or Darwin Core archives and include examining taxon names, the number of biotic interactions, and data structure.

In collaboration with Katja Seltmann, GloBI developer Jorrit Poelen developed bee image packaging workflows in the form of <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/bee-image-finder> and <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/imageseq>. These workflows help researchers to automatically download and package specimen images of interest. Some of these were used to collect image sequences to work towards building, sharing, and citing 3D bee models and their associated data.

In early 2023, Jorrit presented on Big Bee methods to package and cite digital data associated with a bee specimen at Nanosessions #2 and #3 (see <https://nanopub.net/sessions>), organized by Tobias Kuhn, and Philipp von Essen of Knowledge Pixels. Attendees included representatives from the academic publishing industry, researchers, and software/knowledge engineers.

Other work covered the integration of bee type specimens in wikidata for increased exposure (see <https://beehind.org>), developing methods to publish bee traits such as intertegular distance, and presenting at the Native Bee Research Collection Network on 28/30 March 2023.

What opportunities for training and professional development has the project provided?

A weekly meeting via Zoom continues to be an important part of creating Big-Bee workflows, project organization, and onboarding new participants. The Zoom meetings are very well attended by participants, Symbiota Support Hub staff, project consultants, Macropod Solutions staff, and other project collaborators. The meetings also provided a venue for imaging training by Mark Smith (Macroscopic Solutions). They have, and continue to, provide much-needed open office time for questions.

Big-Bee uses Slack software to enhance communication. We presently have **118** members on Slack, including project PIs, collaborators, Symbiota Support Hub staff, undergraduates, and technicians. Slack is being used for day-to-day project management and training/communication about imaging, Notes from Nature, and other project goals.

How have results been disseminated to communities of interest?

- A total of **3** student oral presentations, **3** student posters, **16** student research projects, and **2** published scholarly articles this year.
- Big-Bee was mentioned in **29** academic presentations this year.
- Big-Bee was presented or discussed in **48 events** (i.e., open house, collection tours) across the network, with **5182 attendees**.
- There were **4 articles** about the project in newsletters, periodicals, or other non-scholarly venues.
- The social media hashtag #bigbee, is used on all social media platforms.
- PI Seltmann and Big-Bee partner Erika Tucker collaborated to **co-organize, co-lead, and present** at a comprehensive 2-day workshop focused on various aspects of bee monitoring data management, including data preservation, best practices, standards, sharing, and attribution. The primary aim of this workshop was to enhance existing bee monitoring protocols and establish standardized data collection methods, ultimately facilitating the integration of new data into both internal and shared databases. The workshop's valuable insights are expected to catalyze pre-digitization efforts, ensuring smoother data handling and dissemination. Recordings from the workshop are archived at: <https://www.youtube.com/@nativebeemonitoringRCN/videos>. The September Bee Library portal campaign is one outcome of this workshop.
- Rather than developing independent help resources, Big-Bee is committed to helping develop the Symbiota Support Hub (<https://symbiota.org/help-resources>) and Macroscopic Solutions help resources for the entire community.
- Macroscopic Solutions has created open-source PDFs and tutorial videos describing photogrammetric workflows. These videos are accessible on Macroscopic Solutions Youtube channel and website. Since creating this content, Macroscopic Solutions has seen a sharp increase in academic-based subscriptions. (Examples:

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXhbJ-JirA3-J7FihjXtUyg> and <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn/>)

- Big-Bee is represented via our websites, GitHub project, and data portals (see Products). The Bee Library Symbiota portal was visited by **3,281** users between July 24, 2022 - July 30, 2023, and the number of pageviews was 11,056. A noticeable uptick in views began in June 2023, which corresponds to the time when FSCA started managing data live on the portal. FSCA is the only collection currently managing data live on the Bee Library.

What do you plan to do during the next reporting period to accomplish the goals?

- During the third year of the project, all Big-Bee institutions will focus on reaching their digitization goals, including 3D imaging.
- To facilitate workforce training and digitization, PI Seltmann and Mark Smith (Macropod Solutions) are continuing an online 3D imaging short course to guide institutions in 3D imaging. This will also provide community workforce training.
- We will continue to work closely with our partners at the ASU Symbiota Support Hub to improve image and data searching in the Bee Library portal.
- We will continue Notes from Nature expeditions for body size measurements and label transcriptions.
- Year 3 will focus on trait data, including how to incorporate trait data into the Bee Library Symbiota portal. UCSB postdoctoral researcher Madeline Ostwald will focus on aggregating trait data to include in the portal and as separately published datasets.
- Poelen and Seltmann will continue examining image corpus publication for image datasets, particularly around 3D image models.
- Boost participation in the Bee Library with a Big-Bee Library portal campaign this September.

Cumulative Products

To date, the project has produced 6 peer-reviewed journal publications, 26 posters and talks, and 13 shared datasets or workshop reports.

Journal Paper:

1. Engel, M.S. (2022) New species of the stingless bee genus *Plebeia* (Hymenoptera: Apidae). *Journal of Melittology* 114: 1–28.
2. Baskauf SJ, Girón Duque JC, Nielsen M, Cobb NS, Singer R, Seltmann KC, Kachian Z, Pérez M, Agosti D, Klompen AML (2023) Implementation Experience Report for Controlled Vocabularies Used with the Audubon Core Terms subjectPart and subjectOrientation. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 7: e94188. <https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.7.94188>
3. Ostwald, M. M., Thrift, C. N., & Seltmann, K. C. (2023) Phenotypic divergence in an island bee population: Applying geometric morphometrics to discriminate population-level variation in wing venation. *Ecology and Evolution*, 13, e10085. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.10085>
4. Engel, M.S. (2023) A new species of *Callomegachile* from Larat, Indonesia (Hymenoptera: Megachilidae). *Entomologist's Monthly Magazine* 159(1): 13–18.

Juried Conference Paper:

5. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E (2021) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 5: e74037.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.5.74037>
6. Salim JA, Seltmann KC, Poelen JH, Saraiva AM (2022) Indexing Biotic Interactions in GBIF data. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards* 6: e93565.
<https://doi.org/10.3897/biss.6.93565>

Talks/Posters:

1. Seltmann, KC. (2021) New TCN: Big-Bee. Virtual ADBC Summit. Presentation for iDigBio and the ADBC program. Retrieved from https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/ADBC_Summit_2021 on 21 Sept 2021
2. Seltmann, K.; Allen, J.; Brown, B. V; Carper, A.; Engel, M. S; Franz, N., et al. (2021) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. *Biodiversity Information Science and Standards*, 5(e74037). Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0937b5gp>
3. Gonzalez, VH., Seltmann, KC., Brown, B., Allen, J., Carper, A., Engel, M., et al. (2021) Big-Bee: Una iniciativa para promover el conocimiento de las abejas a través de la digitalización de imágenes y datos de rasgos. ID 112. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0856h3d2>. Poster from XII Congreso Mesoamericano de Abejas Nativas, Centro de Investigaciones Apícolas Tropicales (CINAT), Universidad Nacional, Costa Rica, Nov. 20-21, 2021. The poster is in Spanish.
4. Thrift, C. N. & Seltmann, K. C. (2021) Identifying island-mainland bee populations with wings. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4h46m0ws>
5. Eisner de Eisenhof, L., & Seltmann, K. (2022) Body Size and Taxonomic Influence on Bee Wing Vein Density. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0z73n6vt>
6. Xu, C., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022) Variation of Ocelli Size Between Male and Female Bees in Species of Different Sociality. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0v065150>
7. Wong-Lau, J., Klauke, H., Kaur, H., Alexander, N., Bang, J., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022) Big-Bee: Hair Recognition and Quantification. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0fb1n3pw>
8. Miller, J. T., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022) Environmental Trends in the Distribution of California Bee Species. *UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration*. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/36w6x8pp>
9. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Eldredge T, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Kung GA, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Ostwald MM, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith C, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E. (2022) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. International Union for the Study of Social Insects (IUSSI), San Diego, CA.
10. Allen, J. (2022) Notes from Nature: Goals, Accomplishments and Future Directions. WeDigBio Oct 14th Virtual

11. Seltmann, KC. (2022) Entomological Collections Management Workshop. Big Bee and Terrestrial Parasite Tracker. Retrieved from https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/BioDigiCon_2022 on 22 June 2022
12. Seltmann, KC. (2022) Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization: Big-Bee. Biodiversity Digitization Conference (BioDigiCon) Virtual presentation. Retrieved from https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php/BioDigiCon_2022 on 27 Sept 2022
13. Seltmann, KC. (2022) Extended Thoughts about the Extended Specimen. Biodiversity Digitization Conference (BioDigiCon) Virtual presentation. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0g99h7kf.mp4> on 28 Sept 2022
14. Ostwald MM, Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Eldredge T, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Kung GA, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith C, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E (2022) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. BeeCon, York University, Toronto, CAN. Virtual.
15. Seltmann K.C., Miller J.T. & Poelen J.H. (2022) Global bee interaction database. Entomological Society of America. Vancouver, BC, Canada. November 2022.
16. Seltmann KC, Allen J, Brown BV, Carper A, Eldredge T, Engel MS, Franz N, Gilbert E, Grinter C, Gonzalez VH, Horsley P, Kung GA, Lee S, Maier C, Miko I, Morris P, Oboyski P, Ostwald MM, Pierce NE, Poelen J, Scott VL, Smith C, Smith M, Talamas EJ, Tsutsui ND, Tucker E. (2022) Announcing Big-Bee: An initiative to promote understanding of bees through image and trait digitization. Entomological Society of America. Vancouver, BC, Canada. Poster. November 2022.
17. Seltmann K.C., Paul D. (2023) Lets Talk About Data. Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop. Zoom. March 2023
18. Seltmann K.C. (2023) Big-Bee: Sharing Bee Interactions & Traits. Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop. Zoom. Talk. March 2023
19. Poelen, J. (2023) Bee Species Interactions. Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop. Zoom. Talk. March 2023
20. Jorrit Poelen (2023) was presented virtually at NanoSessions #1 #2 on 2023-02-28/2023-03-28 titled "How Big is That Bee" to help facilitate the publication of Big Bee specimens and traits in semantically Nanopublications. Organized by KnowledgePixel (<https://knowledgepixels.com/>) and attended by Pensoft Publishers (<https://pensoft.net>) among others. See <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/UCSB-IZC00012194/blob/main/nanosessions-presentation-2023-02-28.md> and <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network/UCSB-IZC00012194/blob/main/nanosessions-presentation-2023-03-28.md> for text-based slides
21. C. Palmrose-Krieger, S. Lee and N.M. Franz. (2023) Presented a poster at the 30th Annual School of Life Sciences Undergraduate Research Symposium [Hybrid] on Memorial Union, Ventana Ballroom, Arizona State University, Tempe, Arizona. *Big-Bee: Trait Digitization to Advance Buzz Ecology and Taxonomy Research*. April 2023.
22. Seltmann, KC. (2023) The Pilosity Problem: Using Computer Vision Methods to Define a Complex Phenotype in Bees. Digital Data, June 5-7 2023
23. Ostwald, M. (2023) Toward a global bee functional trait database. Digital Data, June 5-7 2023
24. Miller, JT. Exploring shared life-history strategies as a driver for biodiversity in desert bees & plants. (2023) Digital Data, June 5-7, 2023
25. Seltmann, KC. (2023) New and Current TCNs: Parasite Tracker and Big-Bee. Entomological Collection Managers Workshop, July 19, 2023

26. Smith, C., K. C. Seltmann. (2023) You're it: tagging specimen images in Symbiota to facilitate their use in research. Society for the Preservation of Natural History Collections Annual Meeting, San Francisco, CA. June 1, 2023.

Websites and Data Portals:

Big-Bee project website: <http://big-bee.net>

Bee Library Symbiota Portal: <https://library.big-bee.net>

Big-Bee focused Global Biotic Interactions project page:

<https://www.globalbioticinteractions.org/bigbee>

iDigBio Wiki:

[https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php?title=TCN: Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization \(Big-Bee\)](https://www.idigbio.org/wiki/index.php?title=TCN:_Extending_Anthophila_research_through_image_and_trait_digitization_(Big-Bee))

Big-Bee Network GitHub Project: <https://github.com/Big-Bee-Network>

YouTube (Macroscopic Solutions): <https://macroscopicsolutions.com/video-tutorial-big-bee-tcn;>

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXhbJ-JirA3-J7FihjXtUyg>

Notes from Nature Big-Bee Bonanza project:

<https://www.zooniverse.org/projects/md68135/notes-from-nature-big-bee-bonanza>

Other Publications (Datasets):

1. The full proposal can be found at Seltmann, K. C. (2021) Extending Anthophila research through image and trait digitization (Big-Bee) proposal. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/2vm761mv>
2. Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, University of California Santa Barbara. (2021) UC Santa Barbara Invertebrate Zoology Collection (UCSB-IZC) Data Archive and Biodiversity Dataset Graph (0.1) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5557670>. Data publication that includes full UCSB Invertebrate Zoology Collection image corpus.
3. Seltmann, Katja C., & Poelen, Jorrit H. (2021) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.1.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722445> on 24 Nov 2021
4. Seltmann, Katja C., & Poelen, Jorrit H. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.2.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915003> on 28 Jan 2022
5. Katja C. Seltmann, & Global Biotic Interaction Community. (2022) Global Bee Interaction Data (v2.02) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6564718>
6. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Engel, Michael, & Gonzalez, Victor. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.3.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915012> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5915012> on 28 Jan 2022
7. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, Taro, Engel, Michael, & Gonzalez, Victor. (2022) Big-Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.4.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6950082>
8. Publications of Big Bee Images: Big Bee Community, Poelen, Jorrit H., & Seltmann, Katja. (2022) *Xylocopa sonorina* - UCSB-IZC00012194 - Bee Library - 73e389aa-5886-4c48-8778-ba8932d1bd7e hash://sha256/96bfde1efa599e0e8e61de18b14d61dd308737f684950e4079c04e9bc0f33958 hash://md5/4940f68c84cfa4412f7ffb98bb255bd (0.0.3) [Data set]. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7114665.
9. Seltmann, Katja, Poelen, Jorrit H., UCSB Natural History Collections, & Big Bee Community. (2023) *Halictus ligatus* Halictidae UCSB-IZC00036803 <https://library.big->

bee.net/portal/collections/individual/index.php?occid=72096 Male - Bee Library - 73e389aa-5886-4c48-8778-ba8932d1bd7e
 hash://sha256/3a178bd2f588c35eb9729309d1baa769ea819bcd5bb5142c2de208dd8e299d1a hash://md5/88a7c9b9b2df777a17e707aab635b3ef [Data set]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7510912> .

10. Miller, JT, Poelen, Jorrit, & Seltmann, Katja. (2023) Big Bee Name Alignment Workshop. Zenodo. 10.5281/zenodo.7829969.
11. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, K. Taro, Engel, Michael, Gonzalez, Victor, Knowles, L. Lacey, & Horsley, Pam. (2023) Big Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.7.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7865367
12. Brianne Du Clos, Julien Brun, Sam Droege, Jen Hammock, Andrew Johnston, Jonathan Koch, Clare Maffei, Cynthia Sims Parr, Jorrit H. Poelen, Katja C. Seltmann, & Erika M. Tucker. (2023) US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN Data Management Workshop: Public Domain Videos (1.0.0). Zenodo. doi:10.5281/zenodo.7868217.
13. Seltmann, Katja C., Poelen, Jorrit H., Allen, Julie, Eldredge, K. Taro, Engel, Michael, Gonzalez, Victor, Knowles, L. Lacey, & Horsley, Pam. (2023) Big Bee indexed biotic interactions and review summary (0.8.0) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8184843>

Other Products (Non-scholarly Articles):

1. Shelly Leachman (2021). Creating a Buzz. UCSB Current. Retrieved from <https://www.news.ucsb.edu/2021/020448/creating-buzz> on 27 Oct 2021.
2. Tara Duggan. (2021). To help fight the loss of bees, the California Academy of Sciences to share a 180,000-strong collection online. San Francisco Chronicle. Retrieved from <https://www.sfchronicle.com/climate/article/To-help-fight-loss-of-bees-California-Academy-of-16570034.php> on 2 Nov 2021.
3. Matt Kettmann. Bee Happy. UC Santa Barbara Magazine Retrieved from <https://magazine.ucsb.edu/spring-summer-2022/bee-happy> on July 25, 2022.

Participants

13 institutions are funded by the Big-Bee project (Table 5). Lead participants and institution codes are listed below from each institution. A total of **124** people worked on the Big-Bee project, including PIs, collection managers, students, volunteers, technicians, and postdoctoral scholars (Table 6). **43** undergraduate students received some financial compensation for the project, and **25** students received course credit. **2** graduate students and **2** postdoctoral scholars contributed to the project. These numbers do not include complete statistics for UMMZ, who did not report their participant numbers in time to create the cumulative annual report.

Institution	Institution Code	Participant	Institutional affiliation
Arizona State University	ASUHIC	Nico Franz	School of Life Sciences, Hasbrouck Insect Collection
		Ed Gilbert	School of Life Sciences
		Sangmi Lee	Hasbrouck Insect Collection

California Academy of Sciences	CAS	Chris Grinter	California Academy of Sciences, Entomology
Florida State Collection of Arthropods	FSCA	Elijah Talamas	Florida Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services, Division of Plant Industry
Harvard University	MCZ	Naomi Pierce	Department of Organismic and Evolutionary Biology, Museum of Comparative Zoology
		Crystal Maier	Museum of Comparative Zoology, Entomology
Natural History Museum of Los Angeles County	LACM	Brian Brown	Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County, Entomology
		Giar-Ann Kung	Natural History Museum, Los Angeles County, Entomology
San Diego Natural History Museum	SDMC	Pamela Horsley	San Diego Natural History Museum, Entomology
University of California-Berkeley	EMEC	Neil Tsutsui	Department of Environmental Science, Policy and Management
		Peter Oboyski	Essig Museum of Entomology
University of California, Santa Barbara	UCSB	Katja C Seltmann	Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, Earth Research Institute
University of Colorado, Boulder	UCMC	Adrian Carper	Museum of Natural History, Entomology
		Virginia Scott	Museum of Natural History, Entomology
University of Kansas	SEMC	Michael Engel	Department of Natural Sciences and Mathematics - Ecology & Evolutionary Biology, KU Biodiversity Institute
		Victor Gonzalez-Betancourt	Department of Natural Sciences and Mathematics - Ecology & Evolutionary Biology, KU Biodiversity Institute
University of Michigan Museum of Zoology	UMMZ	L. Lacey Knowles	University of Michigan Museum of Zoology Insect Collection
		Taro Eldredge	University of Michigan Museum of Zoology Insect Collection
University of Nevada, Reno	UNR	Julie Allen	Department of Biology
University of New Hampshire	UNHC	Istvan Miko	Donald S. Chandler Entomological Collection

Table 5: List of project PIs and lead participants at each Big-Bee funded institution.

	UNHC	UMMZI	UCSB	FSCA	UNR	SEMC	SDMC	UCMC	CAS	EMEC	LACM	ASUHIC	MCZ	Total
Undergraduate students hired (i.e., paid)	4		11	0	0	2	0	13	0	7	0	3	3	43
Undergraduate students working for course credit	0		21	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	1	0	25
Undergraduate student volunteers	0		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	4	0	5
Non-student volunteers	1		2	0	0	0	2	1	4	0	0	0	0	10
Total number of undergraduate students	4		32	0	0	2	0	13		10	0	8	3	72
Graduate students	0		0	0	0	2	0	0		0	0	0	0	2
Non-student staff	0	1	3	3	3	0	2	4	3	5	4	3	4	35
Total number of people	5	2	37	3	3	6	4	16	10	15	4	11	8	124

Table 6: Number of people involved in Big-Bee

Partner Organizations

- Notes from Nature
- US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN
- iDigBio
- Biodiversity Information Standards (TDWG)
- Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)
- USGS Native Bee Inventory and Monitoring Lab
- Macroscopic Solutions, LLC

Other Collaborators

Erika Tucker - Terrestrial Parasite Tracker Digitization Taxonomy Manager, Milwaukee Public Museum; Research Associate, Biodiversity Outreach Network (BON)

Hollis Woodard - Assistant Professor, University of California - Riverside; PI USDA US National Native Bee Monitoring RCN (<https://www.usnativebees.com>)

Elizabeth Hill - Agricultural Research Service, US Department of Agriculture
Andrew Johnson - Invertebrate Collections Manager - NEON Biorepository, Arizona State University, Symbiota Support Hub

Andrew Johnson - ASU, Neon Biorepository, Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)

Katie Pearson - Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU); CAP TCN

Lindsay Walker - Symbiota Support Hub (iDigBio & ASU)

Thomas van de Kamp - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Laboratory for Applications of Synchrotron Radiation

Robert Guralnick - Curator of Biodiversity Informatics, Florida Museum of Natural History, University of Florida, iDigBio, Notes from Nature

Bob Blinn - Collection Manager, North Carolina State University Insect Museum

Dylan Valle Rogers - Collaborator, Essig Museum of Entomology

José Augusto Salim - Center on Biodiversity and Computing (www.biocomp.org.br), Universidade de São Paulo

Sophie Cardinal - Canadian National Collection

Keng-Lou James Hung - Assistant Professor of Biology, Oklahoma Biological Survey

Steve Baskauf - Data Science and Data Curation Specialist, Jean & Alexander Heard Libraries, Vanderbilt University; Convener of the TDWG Audubon Core Views Controlled Vocabularies Task Group (<https://github.com/tdwg/ac/blob/master/views/README.md>)

Impacts

What is the impact on the development of the principal discipline(s) of the project?

With GloBI consultant Jorrit Poelen, Big-Bee is demonstrating a distributed system of sharing image and specimen records using linked data using hash technology. The data sharing methodology could facilitate dataset sharing that more accurately keeps track of data provenance. Records and images from the Bee Library are also shared as citable data publications through the Internet Archive and Zenodo. These published archives have a digital identifier (DOI) and an identifier that verifiably identifies the archive content (hash). The archives include metadata describing the origin of the specimen records and images and the records and images themselves. An example of an early published image corpus is available at:

- Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration, University of California Santa Barbara. (2021). UC Santa Barbara Invertebrate Zoology Collection (UCSB-IZC) Data Archive and Biodiversity Dataset Graph (0.2) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5660088>
<https://archive.org/details/preston-ucsb-izchash://sha256/d5eb492d3e0304afadcc85f968de1e23042479ad670a5819cee00f2c2c277f36>
 -
- Big Bee Community, Poelen, Jorrit H., & Seltmann, Katja. (2022) *Xylocopa sonorina* - UCSB-IZC00012194 - Bee Library - 73e389aa-5886-4c48-8778-ba8932d1bd7e hash://sha256/96bfde1efa599e0e8e61de18b14d61dd308737f684950e4079c04e9bc0f33958 hash://md5/4940f68c84cffa4412f7ffb98bb255bd (0.0.3) [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.71146651>

Big-Bee also actively participates in the US Bee Monitoring Research Coordination Network. The impact of our involvement helps bring a specimen-based perspective to ecological research, including the importance of voucher specimens and collections. In addition, PI Seltmann and collaborators Elizabeth Hill, Hollis Woodard, and Erika Tucker developed an extensive two-day workshop on biodiversity data for Bee Monitoring Network participants. This workshop has been identified as the first much-needed data boot camp for over 100 participants from state and federal agencies (i.e., USDA, USGS), universities, non-profits, and many other groups interested in improving the US bee monitoring programs. As a result of the workshop, Big-Bee and the Symbiota Support Hub are launching a data publication campaign for the bee community starting September 1, 2023.

What is the impact on other disciplines?

Big-Bee continues to seek partners for developing artificial intelligence and improved 3D modeling applications using Big-Bee images. Seltmann mentored students from UCSB Statistics and Applied Probability Department for a Data Science Capstone. In 2022 the capstone focused on methods for describing bee hairiness, extracting EXIF data from images, and reading barcodes from images. This is in collaboration with the <https://centralcoastdatascience.org> NSF-supported project. In 2023, the capstone course focused on 3D models and extracting volume data from 3D models. Posters from these capstone courses can be found on the UC eScholarship website:

- Spasibenko, S., Ramayrat, A., Long, W., & Badilla, D. (2023). The Big Bee Project: Advancing Research Through 3D Bee Modeling. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0hd7v9jt>
- Alexander, N., & Seltmann, K. C. (2022). Big-Bee: Towards a More Accurate Hair Quantification Pipeline. UC Santa Barbara: Cheadle Center for Biodiversity and Ecological Restoration. Retrieved from <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/0pw1s0v9>

Big-Bee continues to promote the sharing of images under Creative Commons 0/Public Domain licenses, which already has received attention from MediaWiki and computer vision bee identification initiatives (Brian Spiesman - <https://beemachine.ai>; Automated Wildlife Monitoring - <https://automated-wildlife-cig.github.io>) that are actively searching for open images of bees. Open access to images is also an important impact in the realm of technology transfer.

Big-Bee efforts in image sharing and data reporting led to the improvement of existing open tools like Preston, Nomer, and Elton (see <https://jhpoelen.nl> for more info) to the benefit of other publicly funded projects such as “*Intelligently predicting viral spillover risks from bats and other wild mammals*” (NIH R21 Grant 1R21AI164268-01 - <https://reporter.nih.gov/project-details/10289637>), “*Towards the Web of Biodiversity Knowledge: Understanding Data Connectedness to Improve Identifier Practices*” (NSF OAC 1839201 - https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=1839201), “*Digitizing collections to trace parasite-host associations and predict the spread of vector-borne disease - Parasite Tracker TCN*” (NSF DBI:1901932 - https://www.nsf.gov/awardsearch/showAward?AWD_ID=1901932). A resulting publication that uses Big-Bee data and benefited from the software updates is Elliott, M.J., Poelen, J.H. & Fortes, J.A.B. Signing data citations enables data verification and citation persistence. *Sci Data* 10, 419 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-023-02230-y>

Figure 5: Demographic breakdown of Big-Bee participants based on an anonymous self-reporting survey developed by LACM and UCSB.

What is the impact on the development of human resources?

In our proposal, we committed to recruiting participants from underserved communities using existing programs already found at the collaborating institutions. To track these metrics, Big-Bee created a DEI survey for our annual report. The survey is based on a survey used for the CAP TCN that includes groups defined as underrepresented in Science and Engineering (<https://www.nsf.gov/statistics/2017/nsf17310/digest/introduction>). **124** people were part of this project in the second year. This is an increase from 97 people during year 1. **60%** of the Big-Bee participants are gender minorities in science and engineering (Women, Trans people, etc.), and **17%** are people of color/ racial and ethnic minority groups in science and engineering (Black or African American, Hispanic, Indigenous). **30%** self-described as Asian, and **53%** as White (Figure 5). 101 of the 124 project participants completed the survey and are included in these statistics. The percentage of our reporting participants from minority groups in science and engineering remains consistent with last year.

This year, UCSB awarded three paid, full-time internships for students identified by the UCSB Office of Education Partnerships, Smithsonian Scholars program. The interns are participating in imaging bees and working with Notes from Nature. The Office of Education Partnerships’ mission is to increase college-going rates for low-income students and/or students who will be the first in their families to pursue higher education.

What is the impact on teaching and education experiences?

The collaborative efforts of Big-Bee and its committed team of educators, researchers, and mentors have paved the way for a thriving environment that encourages undergraduate participation in research and fosters the development of future biodiversity experts and collection managers. Undergraduate students make up a large proportion of the workforce in university collections. Big-Bee has already demonstrated a commitment to training the next generation of collection managers and biodiversity researchers about the use and importance of natural history collections. Big-Bee institutions hired **43** undergraduate students, **25** participated for course credit and **5** as volunteers. The students gave **4** oral presentations about Big-Bee

and 5 posters. These numbers are fairly consistent with last year. There was a significant upswing in student research projects during year 2, resulting in 16 projects across the Big-Bee network. Among these projects, 11 were conducted at UCSB, where the 2 project postdoctoral scholars are working. The presence of these postdoctoral scholars has been instrumental in providing mentorship and guidance in undergraduate research initiatives.

Figure 6: Images from Education and Teaching Experiences across the Big-Bee network. The image right includes students at MZC learning curation of museum specimens. Image left UCSB participants visiting LACM to borrow specimens.

UCSB PI Seltmann collaborating with Susan Mazer (UCSB-CAP TCN) to teach a Big-Bee/CAP year-long course in 2022-23 as part of the UCSB Ecology, Evolution and Marine Biology curriculum. 12 students are participating in Course 1 in the series.

Leveraging Biological Collections to Understand the Impacts of Climate Change on the Life Cycles of Plants and Pollinators is a three-quarter series providing hands-on learning and accessible research opportunities in Ecology and Global Change Biology through publicly available data.

Course 1 (Fall 2022)—Applications of biological collections to global change research. Students will cover selected papers that introduce the basics of plant and pollinator developmental biology under climate change, the nature, breadth, and limitations of biological collection data, and how they are applied in global change research today.

Course 2 (Winter 2022)—Data management and analysis in R. Students will develop technical skills in data management and basic statistics necessary for conducting collection-based research. This work will be conducted in the statistical computing language R. Previous programming and statistical training is not required for participating in this course.

Course 3 (Spring 2023)—independent research projects

Students will design and conduct a collection-based research project, crafting hypotheses, choosing appropriate study systems, assessing the fit between research questions and data, and conducting and interpreting their own statistical analyses.

All institutions created value-added activities for undergraduates, staff, and the public, including:

- MCZ organized an insect collecting and preparation workshop for all MCZ summer student interns (Figure 6) and a cross-institution virtual "happy hour" for all students and interns involved with the project.
- ASU hosted an Entomology week for the Biocollections Justice, Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (JEDI) summer research scholars program. Demonstrated and taught collections management, imaging, and digitization activities used for Big Bee with the scholars.
- ASU hosted an Entomology Day for the ASU Art Summer Camp with ASU Natural History Collections. Taught various specimens to learn the diversity of insects, including bees as vital pollinators.
- At UMMZI, graduate curatorial assistant Rachel Wadleigh, and EMU volunteer, Sadie Baker is developing a flexible teaching module for upper-level high school and lower-level undergraduate courses using biodiversity data repositories (iDigBio, GBIF). The module will be designed to explore the effects of climate change in host and species range size using available longitudinal museum data. A beta version will be shared with the Big-Bee group for comments and made publicly available.
- Dylan Bergersen (and other departmental staff) participated in Bug themed nightlife at the Cal Academy on Thursday, June 2nd titled "Buggin Out" <https://www.calacademy.org/nightlife/nightlife-buggin-out> Drawers of bees were included with specimens for a live tabling event.
- A. Carper (PI) has included the project in three outreach events to foster interest in our future Notes from Nature expeditions:
 - CU Boulder Mountain Research Station 100th Anniversary Seminar Series (6/21/2022): Colorado's Wild Bees Expanding the Conservation Impacts of Pollinator Research
 - CU Conference on World Affairs Panel (4/8/2022): Silent Farm: Saving our Birds, Bees, Frogs, and Ourselves
 - People & Pollinators Action Network Webinar (4/7/2022): Challenges in Conserving Colorado's Native Bees
- SDMC held 2 training sessions for Entomology new hires and department staff on using Macropod imaging system. Molly Rightmyer Gee (Osmia expert) held a training session with Ellie Deer (project staff) on basic bee morphology and identification.
- Horsley (SDMC) participated in IUSSI meeting at SDNHM by having a booth and discussing Big-Bee Project with attendees.

What is the impact on physical resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on institutional resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on information resources that form infrastructure?

Nothing to report.

What is the impact on technology transfer?

Our portal is managed by the Symbiota Support Hub (ASU & iDigBio), which hosts the majority of the Symbiota portals at this time. Because of the Hub experience, we can contribute to and benefit from NEON and the portal advances from other TCNs. We are building off of the trait module started from the CAP TCN and the interactions with Global Biotic Interactions originally initiated by the Tri-Tropic TCN and further developed during the Parasite Tracker TCN. Symbiota users can also access developments and innovations during the Big-Bee project through our GitHub repository.

Big-Bee provided the newly funded iDigBee TCN with imaging workflows. Members of iDigBees are participating in our Slack, and we plan to share data between the two projects. MCZ is also instrumental to the NSF-funded "LightningBug" project, which aims to develop an imaging system that captures images of specimens and their labels in 3-D, to reconstruct the labels in a flat, computer-readable form. MZC will connect efforts and aid in exchanging ideas between Big-Bee and LightningBug.

Big-Bee drove the development of the Macropod 3D modeling system through user testing, which led to innovations in this technology. These innovations improved the product for all future users, including updates to the workflows and hardware. Some modifications to 3D modeling for small, hairy objects used by Big-Bee were incorporated into Agisoft Metashape 2.0 released in February 2023.

What is the impact on society beyond science and technology?

One of the largest impacts of the project is our commitment to increasing awareness about bees and other insects in our communities. This comes through outreach events, including support for Xerxes Society conservation initiatives such as the Bee Campus program, pollinator gardens, or bug-themed museum events. A total of **5182** people attended Big-Bee related events. A few examples from this year include:

- Essig Museum has an ongoing Pollinator Garden project as part of a Xerxes Society Bee Campus. Students plant and manage native California plants in a demonstration garden on the UC Berkeley campus and collect qualitative and quantitative data on flower-visiting insects.
- Essig Museum led an entomology lecture and field experience for the California Naturalist certification course at UC Santa Cruz. This ten-week course exposes students to California ecosystems, flora, and fauna. The entomology section focuses on the diversity and role of insects, including as vital pollinators for native and agricultural plants.

What percentage of the award's budget was spent in a foreign country?

Nothing to report.

Changes/Problems

We have nothing to report for changes in approach, expenditure impact, care of human subjects, care of vertebrate animals, or changes in the use of biohazards.

Actual or Anticipated problems or delays and actions or plans to resolve them:

Macroscopic Solutions has experienced some delays related to equipment maintenance and method changes from 2022 – 2023. Several users reported error 20 and 30 codes on camera bodies resulting from shutter failures caused by the high volume of images required for 3D photogrammetry per specimen. There are approximately 2000-8000 individual images captured for each 3D model reconstruction. Repairs required 10 days to complete, and camera body loans were given to mitigate project downtime. Macroscopic Solutions responded very quickly to support requests and, in many cases, sends a loaner camera or flash during repairs. Because of this and the efforts of the individual partner institutions, delays have been minimized.